

Reconditioning of the Leuven Isotope Separator as a test bench for radioactive ion beam development

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Abstract

Producing novel medical radionuclides in the quantities necessary for pre-clinical and clinical use requires an ion source able to handle high ion throughputs, operated efficiently, to deliver high specific activity samples. This is only possible with the understanding of how different parameters affect the ion source performance. Offline mass separators are needed to run systematic studies that would help us to derive the laws governing those ion sources. At KU Leuven, we are refurbishing the Leuven Isotope Separator, a mass separator previously used for implantations of radioisotopes in solid-state samples and Mössbauer spectroscopy. In the past couple of years, the machine has undergone significant updates and has been adapted to integrate the target ion source units used at ISOLDE, CERN. This paper discusses the modifications to the Leuven Isotope Separator, as well as its potential as a test bench for the study of radioactive ion beams in the future.

Keywords: Mass separation, Ion source development, Radionuclide production

1. Introduction

Radionuclides have already revolutionised the diagnosis and treatment of cancer patients [1]. Some of the novel medical radionuclides can only be made using the Isotope Separation Online (ISOL) technique [2]. The radioactive species collected for medical applications need to be isotopically pure which requires mass separation [3, 1]. Terbium has been identified as a particularly promising radionuclide family – there is a quadruplet of isotopes that can be used for both diagnostics and therapy [4]. However, there is a bottleneck when it comes to terbium production – it is challenging to extract from the target and ionize because of its refractory nature and chemistry. This is especially detrimental when it comes to the alpha-emitter, Tb-149, which could fill the gap in the targeted alpha therapy [5]. The half-life of Tb-149 is only 4.1 h which means that it must be extracted rapidly to avoid losses due to radioactive decay.

In order to be able to produce short-lived radionuclides, we need to understand how to extract and ionize them quickly and efficiently. Systematic studies are necessary to develop an understanding of the parameter space and limitations faced by different ion sources and target materials. Looking at collections of different radionuclides performed at CERN-MEDICIS [3], it is evi-

dent that each isotope faces a different set of limitations [1, 6, 7]. Those limitations depend on the production route, the target material and the ion source used, as well as the isotope's half-life, amongst other factors. Due to operational constraints and limited understanding of the ion sources, detangling the effects of those parameters is very difficult at production facilities such as MEDICIS. Consequently, extensive studies at offline facilities are crucial to improve and optimise production of different radionuclides. Motivated by this, Leuven Isotope Separator (LIS) is in the process of being reconditioned as a test bench for radioactive ion beam development of Forced Electron Beam Induced Arc Discharge FEBIAD ion sources [8] and high-throughput surface sources. It is also planned to be used for implantation of isotopically pure samples.

2. The frontend

The LIS frontend has undergone several upgrades since the start of this project. The goal was to integrate the CERN-ISOLDE [9] target ion source unit into the pre-existing frontend and restart the machine. The front-end houses a two-step extraction system and an einzel lens with a set of x-y deflectors. All of the aforementioned

Figure 1: Technical drawing of the original LIS frontend, with some of the changes visible on the overlapped CAD model.

elements can move together such that the distance between the aperture of the ion source and that of the extraction electrode can be varied between 4.2 ± 0.5 cm and 14.2 ± 0.5 cm. This means that the beam tune through the frontend remains constant when the distance between the ion source and the extraction electrode is adjusted. The einzel lens consists of three cylinders of varying size, with the third cylinder (furthest away from the ion source) encompassing two sets of deflectors, allowing for correction along the x and y-axis (z-axis is the beam axis). This is presented in Fig.1, where the original technical drawing has been overlaid with a 3D model that includes the upgrades such as the new ion source and the new extraction electrode.

In order to couple the target unit to the frontend, a custom connection piece was designed, see Fig.2. The shape and the position of the extraction electrode play a crucial role in ion beam formation [10, 11]. Since the ion source is rigidly fixed in position inside of the target unit and the distance between the apertures is optimised at 6 cm, the extraction electrode had to be redesigned to reach the required position. The new extraction electrode is a hybrid of the previous LIS design and the current ISOLDE extraction electrode design, shown in Fig. 3. The electrode is made out of stainless steel and the ISOLDE-based tip is screwed onto the original LIS

Figure 2: ISOLDE target unit with custom made connection designed for LIS frontend.

cone, which means that it can be easily replaced. Downstream, another electrode can be used for acceleration and further shaping of the beam.

A new LabView-based data acquisition system was installed and has been commissioned. All the elements on the high voltage platform, but not the high voltage power supplies themselves, are powered by a motor generator. The motor and the generator belong to the original installation and have been purchased sep-

Figure 3: The new extraction electrode design which is a hybrid between the original LIS extraction electrode and the ISOLDE extraction electrode. The electrode is made of stainless steel and is mirror polished.

arately, with the connection in-between them designed and made in-house. For target cooling, a water-to-air chiller has been installed inside the Faraday cage to eliminate the need for deionised water.

Originally, the vacuum system consisted of a pre-pump and two turbo pumps. Turbo 2 on Fig.1 was removed to make space for the table supporting the ion source. This was needed as the ISOLDE target units are much heavier than the ion source used in the past. With one turbo pump, high-vacuum of $< 2 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar is achieved, which is sufficient to hold high-voltage up to 50 kV tested so far, and to operate the ion source.

3. Simulations

SIMION simulations were performed in order to obtain initial voltages needed to transmit the beam from the ion source to the Faraday cup, as shown in Fig.4. The source was built and tested at CERN, and the parameters used at the ISOLDE OFFLINE 1 separator were then used as the starting point of the simulations. The whole system was built using geometry (.GEM) files, so that any possible misalignments can be investigated, and any modifications can be implemented easily.

4. First tests

The target ion source unit was prepared with three mass markers of lithium, sodium and cesium, in order to make an ion beam. Initial tests were performed to form an ion beam and observe a current signal on the picoammeter connected to the Faraday cup indicated in Fig.1. During these tests, the einzel lens voltage was scanned between 0 and 25 kV for extraction voltages of 10, 15,

Figure 4: The frontend geometry in SIMION, with potential surface shown underneath it and field lines and beam trajectories plotted for both. With CERN Offline 1 parameters, we expect the beam to reach the Faraday cup. Those parameters were used as initial voltages for first beam tests.

20, 22, 25, 35 kV. The position of the extraction electrode was scanned at 20 and 25 kV. However, no signal was observed on the Faraday cup at any point. Several tests were then planned including using the extraction electrode as a Faraday cup, and placing thermal paper at the exit of the frontend to obtain beam marks. None of the foreseen diagnostics tests could be performed, however, due to the malfunctioning of the motor generator. We are in the process of exploring replacements, such as a separation transformer as used in other facilities.

5. Conclusions & Outlook

LIS has undergone substantial upgrades to make it compatible with the ISOLDE target and ion source units. As of right now, a beam at the Faraday cup has not been detected and any attempts were halted by the failure of the motor generator. After this is rectified, troubleshooting can begin. In the future, the machine is planned to be used for radioactive ion beam development. Particularly, systematic studies on the FEBIAD ion source developed at CERN are planned once the machine is characterized. One of the studies planned is looking at the effect of the buffer gas on the ionisation efficiency and the relationship between the ionisation potential of the buffer gas and the beam [12]. LIS is also intended to be used as a test bench for ion sources developed for ISOL@MYRRHA [13] and to investigate radioactive sample separation, such as K-40 for muon atom spectroscopy [14].

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